

Role of Metal Ions in Reactions of dl-Camphorquinone with Monoamines

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The condensation of monoamines with dl-camphorquinone in the presence of metal ions (Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+}) gave two classes of metal complexes. The reactions leading to Class I complexes gave monoimines with the imino group at C(2) and C(3) positions. The reactions leading to Class II complexes gave monoimines with the imino group at C(3) position only, similar to that obtained by the direct condensation reaction in the absence of a metal ion. A diimine is also obtained in a reaction involving copper(II) complexes of Class I.

FORSTER¹ has noted that d-camphorquinone reacts with aniline forming an imine group only at the C(3) position, this site being sterically least hindered. However, in the condensation reaction of d-camphorquinone with *ortho*-phenylenediamine, both the carbonyl groups at C(2) and C(3) participate in an imine formation reaction yielding d-camphorquinoxaline². The effect of R group (in RNH_2) on the imine formation reaction would therefore enlighten the steric details in d-camphorquinone. Further variations in the steric factors can be introduced by carrying these reactions in the presence of metal ions. In the later reactions it may be possible to separate the Schiff base complexes. This paper reports the results of study of this problem.

Experimental

Infrared spectra were measured in the range 400-4000 cm^{-1} on a Perkin-Elmer grating infrared spectrometer 337 for the nujol and hexachlorobutadiene mulls. Hydrogen-1 nmr spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer at 90 MHz using CDCl_3 as solvent and tetramethylsilane for lock signal.

All the chemicals were of AnalaR B.D.H. grade and of Aldrich Chemicals. dl-Camphorquinone was prepared by the direct oxidation of dl-camphor using Riley's selenium dioxide method³.

Synthesis of metal complexes: All the complexes were prepared by using a similar procedure. A typical procedure for the condensation of dl-camphorquinone with aniline in the presence of nickel chloride is given below.

To a solution of nickel chloride (2.39 g; 0.01 mole) in methanol (20 ml) was added slowly, with constant stirring, a solution of dl-camphorquinone (3.32 g; 0.02 mole) in methanol (20 ml) and of aniline (3.72; 0.04 mole) in methanol (10 ml). A suspension of sodium acetate in methanol was

added to this mixture with constant stirring and the mixture was refluxed on water bath for 20 hr. The mixture was brought to room temperature and was filtered. The mother liquor was reduced to a small volume *in vacuo*, and residue was extracted with *n*-hexane (extract P). The residue from this stage was extracted with benzene (extract Q). The residue from this treatment was further extracted with chloroform giving extract R. The residue from this final treatment was discarded.

The extract P was chromatographed on a neutral alumina packed column. Elution with *n*-hexane gave two fractions. The first fraction was of unreacted dl-camphorquinone and the second fraction gave the Schiff base (IIA). The elution with benzene-*n*-hexane mixture (1:4 v/v) gave the Schiff base (IIB).

The extract Q was reduced to a small volume *in vacuo* and was washed with *n*-hexane yielding the yellow crystals of 10. The extract R was reduced to a small volume *in vacuo* and was washed with benzene yielding the yellowish-green crystals of 10a.

During the synthesis of copper(II) complexes, the compounds obtained from extracts Q and R were further washed five to six times with diethyl-ether.

The reactions in which α -diiminocamphor, C, was formed, the compound C was obtained in a fraction eluted with benzene-*n*-hexane (1:1 v/v) after the separations of A and B isomeric imines from extract P using a neutral alumina-packed column.

Separation of ligand from complex: The chloroform solution of the complex was treated with a suspension of sodium acetate in methanol and 1M acetic acid in methanol. The mixture was stirred for 8 hr at room temperature. The mixture was reduced to a small volume *in vacuo* and was extracted with *n*-hexane. The extract was chromatographed on neutral alumina-packed column separating the isomeric imines.

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Synthesis of Schiff bases : A mixture of purified amine (0.2 mole) and dl-camphorquinone (0.1 mole) in methanol was refluxed on water-bath for 20 hr. The solvent was removed *in vacuo* at room temperature and the residue was chromatographed on neutral alumina-packed column. Elution with *n*-hexane gave a first fraction of unreacted dl-camphorquinone and second fraction was of a Schiff base with imine group at C(3) position (compound A).

Results and Discussion

The direct reaction of dl-camphorquinone with *n*-butyl amine gave a product (IA) which showed a single band due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$. Its ^1H nmr spectra showed three signals of equal intensity at τ 9.22, 9.05 and 8.94 which were assigned to the methyl groups at C(10), C(8) and C(9) respectively. On the basis of analytical data and the Foster's¹ suggestion we tentatively assigned the imine group formation at C(3) position (compound A).

When one mole of nickel chloride was treated with two moles of dl-camphorquinone and four moles of *n*-butyl amine, a single complex (9) was separated, and its chemical analysis suggested that one nickel ion had coordinated, in effect, with one ligand moiety obtained from dl-camphorquinone. The organic compound separated during this reaction was found to contain one imine group in every ligand molecule. However, its ^1H nmr spectra showed three signals of equal intensity at τ 9.17, 9.02 and 8.98 in addition to the signals observed for compound (IA); the intensities of these additional signals were about 80 per cent that of the other three signals. These results suggested that when the condensation of α -diketone with *n*-butyl amine was carried out in the presence of nickel(II), both the C(2) and C(3) carbonyl groups participated in the Schiff base formation. We tentatively associated these additional ^1H nmr signals to compound IB containing an imine group at C(2) position. Similarly the $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ observed at the higher frequency was assigned to this compound. We were, however, unsuccessful in separating the proposed isomeric imines IA and IB by the chromatographic techniques or solubility differences.

Infrared spectra of the complex (9) showed two bands at 1728 and 1738 cm^{-1} due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$. Its ^1H nmr spectra displayed the broad signals probably due to the paramagnetic nature of the complex in solution. The complex (9) was therefore a mixture of two ligand-isomeric complexes containing ligands with configurations (A) and (B). These results suggested that the so called steric factors prevalent in the direct condensation reaction were modified in the presence of nickel(II). It will therefore be profitable to study the imine condensation reactions of dl-camphorquinone in the presence of different metal ions to analyse whether it would be possible to separate the isomeric imines. These condensation reactions were carried out in the

presence of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) chlorides and iodides using *n*-butyl amine, aniline, *o*-toluidine, *m*-toluidine and α -naphthylamine.

On the basis of the elemental analysis, the complexes prepared in the present work were grouped into two classes: Class I, LMX_2 ; Class II, L_2MX_2 , L being the Schiff base and X being the halide group (Fig. 1). The complexes of Class I and Class II displayed characteristically different infrared spectra in the region 1755-1630 cm^{-1} (Table 1). Since $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ for Class II complexes was not much shifted from that observed for the free ligand, the carbonyl group in these complexes was not participating in coordination (or metal-oxygen bond was weak). The second carbonyl group was participating in the imine condensation reaction, and it was coordinated to the metal ion. Since $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ in Class I complexes showed a large shift to a lower frequency and a decrease in intensity, it was probably participating in metal-ligand bonding². The intensity of $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ was comparatively high. The Schiff base in these complexes probably behaved as a bidentate ligand, unlike its behaviour as a monodentate ligand in Class II complexes.

The complexes of both the classes were soluble in organic solvents such as benzene and chloroform and they gave non-conducting solutions in nitromethane. The halide groups in these complexes, therefore, participated in metal-ligand bonding, and probably behaved as monodentate ligand (the bridged halide complexes of Schiff bases are generally negligibly soluble in organic solvents). Thus the Class I complexes were four coordinated; the metal ion in Class II complexes displayed potentially four coordination number.

The nature of metal-ligand bonding in Class I and Class II complexes was further analysed by using the analytical data of the Schiff bases separated from the complexes and of the Schiff bases obtained from *n*-hexane washings of the complexes during synthesis. The Schiff bases obtained from Class II complexes showed three ^1H nmr signals in the region τ 8.70-9.30 of equal intensity. Infrared spectra of these Schiff bases also showed only one band due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$. These results suggested that only one carbonyl group at one specific position had participated in the imine condensation reaction. We tentatively proposed the presence of an imine group at C(3) position in these compounds.

The Schiff bases separated from the Class I complexes showed two closely spaced $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ group frequencies and a hump was observed on a band associated with $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ (Table 2). ^1H NMR spectra of these ligands showed three additional signals of equal intensity in the high field region corresponding to CH_3 group. These results suggested that the ligand separated from these complexes was a mixture of two isomeric imines. Thus the complexes of Class I were a mixture of isomeric complexes - one isomer containing an imine group

Fig. 1. Reactions of dl-camphorquinone with primary amines. Class I complexes : $\text{M}=\text{Co(II)}$, $\text{R}=\textit{n}$ -butyl ; $\text{M}=\text{Ni(II)}$, $\text{R}=\textit{n}$ -butyl, phenyl, 2-methylphenyl, 3-methylphenyl ; $\text{M}=\text{Cu(II)}$, $\text{R}=\textit{n}$ -butyl, phenyl. Class II Complexes : $\text{M}=\text{Co(II)}$, $\text{R}=\text{phenyl}$, 2-methylphenyl, 3-methylphenyl, α -naphthyl, $\text{M}=\text{Ni(II)}$, $\text{R}=\alpha$ -naphthyl ; $\text{M}=\text{Cu(II)}$, $\text{R}=\text{2-methylphenyl}$, 3-methylphenyl, α -naphthyl. $\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$ or I^- .

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF METAL COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Complex#	Colour	m.p. °C	IR spectral data	
				$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})/\text{cm}^{-1}$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})/\text{cm}^{-1}$
1.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{CoCl}_2$	red	93-95	1668(s)	1724(w), 1736(w)
2.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2^*$	violet	105-107	1653(m)	1748(s)
3.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{CoI}_2$	violet	118-120	1672(m)	1750(s)
4.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{-}m\text{-CH}_3)_2\text{CoCl}_2$	violet	165-167	1635(m)	1747(s)
5.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{-}m\text{-CH}_3)_2\text{CoI}_2$	violet	180-182	1664(m)	1744(s)
6.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2\text{CoCl}_2$	red	202-204	1652(m)	1750(s)
7.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2\text{CoI}_2$	red	246-248	1690(m)	1752(s)
8.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{-}o\text{-CH}_3)_2\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-}o\text{-CH}_3\text{NH}_2^{**}$	violet	118-120	1689(m)	1755(s)
9.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{NiCl}_2$	yellowish green	89-90	1650(s)	1728(m), 1738(w)
10.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{NiCl}_2$	yellow	118-120	1669(s)	1726(s)
10a.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{NiCl}_2$	yellowish green	128-129	1665(s)	1740(w)
11.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{NiI}_2$	green	158-159	1658(s)	1720(m), 1733(w)
12.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{-}m\text{-CH}_3)_2\text{NiCl}_2$	pale yellow	123-124	1659(s)	1722(w), 1736(w)
13.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{-}m\text{-CH}_3)_2\text{NiI}_2$	green	180-182	1661(s)	1723(m), 1735(w)
14.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2\text{NiCl}_2$	yellowish green	193-195	1640(m)	1750(s)
15.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_{10}\text{H}_7)_2\text{NiI}_2$	yellow	228-229	1667(m)	1742(s)
16.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{-}o\text{-CH}_3)_2\text{NiCl}_2$	green	136-138	1662(s)	1730(w), 1740(w)
17.	$(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{ONn-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2\text{CuCl}_2$	green	103-104	1663(s)	1730(m), 1739(w)

(Table 1 Contd.)

18.	(C ₁₀ H ₁₄ ONC ₆ H ₅) ₂ CuCl ₂	dark green	138-140	1677(s)	1729(w)
18a.	(C ₁₀ H ₁₄ ONC ₆ H ₅) ₂ CuCl ₂	dark green	145-146	1675(s)	1740(w)
19.	(C ₁₀ H ₁₄ ONC ₆ H ₅) ₂ CuI ₂	dark green	155-157	1690(s)	1728(w), 1740(w)
20.	(C ₁₀ H ₁₄ ONC ₆ H ₄ <i>m</i> -CH ₃) ₂ CuCl ₂	dark green	132-133	1659(m)	1752(s)
21.	(C ₁₀ H ₁₄ ONC ₆ H ₄ <i>m</i> -CH ₃) ₂ CuI ₂	dark green	145-146	1685(m)	1749(s)
22.	(C ₁₀ H ₁₄ ONC ₆ H ₄ <i>o</i> -CH ₃) ₂ CuCl ₂	green	155-157	1633(m)	1747(s)
23.	(C ₁₀ H ₁₄ ONC ₆ H ₄ <i>o</i> -CH ₃) ₂ CuI ₂	dark green	180-182	1664(m)	1748(s)
24.	(C ₁₀ H ₁₄ ONC ₆ H ₄ <i>o</i> -CH ₃) ₂ CuCl ₂	dark green	122-123	1637(m)	1750(s)

‡ All metal complexes gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

* $\nu(N-H)/cm^{-1}$ 3253(m), 3108(m).

** $\nu(N-H)/cm^{-1}$ 3258(m), 3282(m).

TABLE 2 - PHYSICAL DATA OF SCHIFF BASES SEPARATED FROM COMPLEXES

Compound No.*	Molecular Formula‡	Colour	m.p. °C	Spectral data				
				$\tau(C=O)$ †	$\tau(C=N)$ †	$\tau(C=O)$ †	$\nu(C=N)/cm^{-1}$	$\nu(C=O)/cm^{-1}$
IA	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ NO	yellow	b.p. 50** 1 × 10 ⁻³ mm	9.22	9.05	8.94*	1666(s)	1744(vs)
IB	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ NO	orange	b.p. 50** 1 × 10 ⁻³ mm	9.17	9.02	8.98*	1666(s)	1766(s)
IC	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ N ₂	yellow	59-61	9.19	9.03	8.88	1708(vs)	—
IIA	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO	dark yellow	116-117	9.12	9.04	8.87	1662(vs)	1746(vs)
IIB	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO	pale yellow	122-123	9.10	9.02	8.93	1676(m)	1748(vs)
IIC	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ N ₂	orange	137-139	9.11	9.04	8.82	1708(vs)	—
IIIA	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ NO	red	142-143	9.15	9.04	8.90	1671(vs)	1759(vs)
IIIA + IIIB	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ NO	red	141-149	complex multiplets			1663(m)	1750(s)
IVB	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ NO	red	137-138	complex multiplets			1674(m)	1763(m)
IVB + IVB	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ NO	red	139-145	complex multiplets			1654(sh)	1755(vs)
VA	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ NO	orange	153 dec	9.21	9.11	8.86	1675(m)	1752(vs)
							1678(m)	1758(vs)
							1674(sh)	1753(vs)
							1696(s)	—

* IA, 3-N-(*n*-butyl)dl-camphorquinoneimine, IB, 2-N-(*n*-butyl)dl-camphorquinoneimine, IC, 2,3-N-(*n*-butyl)dl-camphorquinonediimine, IIA, 3-N-(phenyl)dl-camphorquinoneimine, IIB, 2-N-(phenyl)dl-camphorquinoneimine, IIC, 2,3-N-(phenyl)dl-camphorquinonediimine, IIIA, 3-N-(2-methylphenyl)dl-camphorquinoneimine, IIIB, 2-N-(2-methylphenyl)dl-camphorquinoneimine, IVA, 3-N-(3-methylphenyl)dl-camphorquinoneimine, IVB, 2-N-(3-methylphenyl)dl-camphorquinoneimine, VA, 3-N-(1-naphthyl)dl-camphorquinoneimine.

‡ All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

† τ Values of CH₃ relative to TMS in CDCl₃.

* Triplet at τ 9.15, 9.11 and 9.07 in the intensity ratio 1 : 2 : 1 for CH₂ of *n*-butyl group

** The exact b.p. of imines could not be determined as they decompose even under high vacuum.

at C(3) and a carbonyl group at C(2), and the other isomer containing an imine group at C(2) and a carbonyl group at C(3). These observations prompted us to do a careful separation of the complexes and of the imines separated from the complexes.

The complexes prepared in the present work were found to decompose on both silica and neutral alumina columns, and fractional crystallisation from different organic solvents seemed to be the only method for the separation of the ligand-isomeric complexes. We were successful in separating copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes containing the imines obtained from the condensation of aniline and dl-camphorquinone. One of the two isomeric complexes was more soluble in benzene. Infrared spectra of these isomeric complexes showed a single band associated with $\nu C=O$. The ligands separated from these complexes displayed only three characteristic signals due to CH₂ groups (Table 2).

From the *n*-hexane washing of the complexes, it was possible to separate imines on neutral alumina-packed column. The washings of Class II complexes gave only one imine, and its ir and ¹H nmr spectra were identical with those separated from the corresponding complexes. From the *n*-hexane washings of Class I complexes two imines corresponding to formula A and B were separated (Table 2). From the *n*-hexane washings of copper(II) complexes, in addition to the isomeric imines, an appreciable amount of an imine which did not show any band due to $\nu C=O$ was obtained. It showed two strong bands due to $\nu C=N$ group, one at 1708 cm⁻¹ and the other in the region 1662-1671 cm⁻¹. The new imine contained the imine groups both at C(2) and C(3) positions (formula C). However, a complex containing this ligand was not detected, both from the ir spectra of the complexes and from the spectroscopic properties of the ligands separated from the corresponding complexes.

The crude product of the Schiff base complexes of copper(II) showed a medium to weak intensity band in the region 2136-2146 cm^{-1} . This band disappeared after repeated triturations with diethylether. The presence of this band in the infrared spectra of the crude compound suggested the formation of nitrile⁶ from the coordinated ketoimine through the successive steps of the formation of copper(II)-Schiff base complex, oxidation of this complex to copper(III)-Schiff base complex, followed by a two-electron transition forming copper(I)-nitrile complex⁷.

The direct condensation reaction of dl-camphorquinone with amine always gave only one imine which was characterised as a compound containing imine group at C(3) position (formula A). In these condensation reactions proper care was taken to avoid the presence of even microamounts of transition metal ions. For example, the condensation reaction of dl-camphorquinone with aniline containing a trace amount of copper(II) as an impurity led to the formation of a mixture of isomeric imines. These results suggested that the groups at both C(2) and C(3) should participate in coordination for the formation of isomeric imines.

The role of the metal ion in the formation of isomeric imines seemed to be stereo-electronic. The d-camphorquinone itself displayed an interesting stereochemistry. The observation of isorotation points in the concentration dependent rotatory dispersion curves of d-camphorquinone in *n*-heptane⁸ indicated an equilibrium between two stereoisomers. The difference in the polarization of CH_3 groups at 8 and 9 positions by the groups at 2 and 3 positions was indicated from the solvent effect on ^1H nmr spectra of d-camphorquinone and was further confirmed by a large difference ($\Delta\tau=0.48$) in the ^1H signals of these methyl groups in d-camphorquinoxaline⁹. Such polarisation effects were also displayed by the Schiff bases separated in the present work. The decreasing trend of the difference of the shielding of the two axial methyl groups was as follows :

1-naphthylimine > phenylimine > 3-methylphenylimine > 2-methylphenylimine > *n*-butylimine

The role of the coordinated metal ion was probably to minimise the stereo-electronic differences between the axial methyl groups, and on coordination both the groups at C(2) and C(3) would have more or less similar reactivity. So the complexes in which the groups at C(2) and C(3) were coordinated, (Class I complexes), the imine reaction took place at these groups. A small difference in stereoelectronic factors at C(2) and C(3) was, however, reflected in the relative yields of the two imines as the yield of isomer B was about 80 per

cent that of isomer A. A similar stereoelectronic equivalence at the coordinated centres was proposed in the transamination reaction^{10,11}.

In the imine condensation reaction of dl-camphorquinone with *n*-butyl amine and aniline in presence of copper(II) a compound containing imine groups both at C(2) and C(3) (compound C) was separated, while the corresponding copper(II) complex was not separated. However, it seemed that this Schiff base formation reaction proceeded through a transition state consisting of the formation of a α -diimine metal complex, since a direct condensation of dl-camphorquinone and amine did not give a compound containing imine groups both at C(2) and C(3). Similarly, the formation of Schiff base with formula B also proceeded through a complex formation reaction. One might say therefore with caution that these reactions were the homogeneous catalytic reactions.

While preparing this manuscript a work was cited reporting the reaction of d-camphorquinone with 1,3-propanediamine in the presence of nickel nitrate¹². It was proposed that the complex obtained from this reaction contained an imine group at C(3) position. We are, however, successful in separating compounds containing imine groups at both C(2) and C(3) positions using diamines also ; these results will be reported later.

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